

Federated learning (FL) enables collaborative model training without centralizing sensitive data, yet remains vulnerable to Byzantine clients that submit poisoned or manipulated gradients. Existing defenses typically rely on single-signal anomaly detectors (e.g., gradient distance or magnitude), achieving false accept rates (FAR) of 15–81% against sophisticated attacks while incorrectly rejecting 18–35% of honest participants under realistic non-IID distributions.

We present ZK-Sentry, a practical Byzantine-robust FL system that combines fixed-scale gradient encoding, multi-modal gradient analysis, Groth16 zero-knowledge proofs, and adaptive Bayesian reputation tracking. Our central insight is that Byzantine gradients exhibit simultaneous anomalies across multiple independent signals, making evasion fundamentally harder than defeating any single detector. ZK-Sentry fuses five signals—spectral signature (15%), magnitude distribution (35%), sign consistency (10%), temporal stability (15%), and peer divergence (25%)—into a weighted scoring mechanism that forces attackers to satisfy all constraints concurrently. Reputation-aware ZK proofs (3,714 constraints: 1,671 nonlinear, 2,043 linear) allow clients to prove per-update quality without revealing gradients, while adaptive verification thresholds reduce false-rejection rates by 83–100% for long-term honest participants.

We implement an end-to-end prototype with gas-optimized Ethereum smart contracts, an off-chain aggregator using Krum-based Byzantine-robust aggregation, and Circom/Groth16 circuits. Evaluation on MNIST, CIFAR-10, and FEMNIST under 10× gradient-amplification poisoning and targeted backdoor attacks demonstrates cross-dataset generalization using a single detector configuration: FAR = 0–1% (vs. 75–81% for single-signal baselines) and FRR = 1.7–16.8% (vs. 18–22% baseline). Zero-knowledge proof generation requires 628 ms \pm 45 ms (Intel i7-10700K) with 14 ms on-chain verification and \approx 180k gas per update.